

Healing Plants, Tamed Poisons: Ecofeminist Resistance in Women Romantic Poets

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Abstract: *Opium narratives have been an integral part of Romantic poetry and imagination. Traditionally this discourse has been dominated by male poets who portrayed opium as a drug which was used as a tool for escapism. This phenomenon kept the medicinal use of opium marginalized as it was garnered by women in their domestic space as a herb, in complete contrast to the capitalization of opium as a drug with unethical mass production. This paper studies the domestication of opium by representative women Romantic poets not as a production of colonial and masculine imagination but as an ethical, domesticated and community substance used for its healing properties. The paper theorises its core argument with reference to ecofeminist Vandana Shiva's ideas of nature and women being exploited by patriarchy and capitalism which critiques patriarchal science and emphasizes on the domestic space of women led community based medicines that aligns with the ecofeminist resistance portrayed by women Romantic poets. The paper aims to look at opium beyond its canonical depiction of a frenzy-causing drug by the masculine imagination and in the context of its ethical and sustainable use as a healing plant harvested in feminine domestic space.*

Keywords: Ecofeminism, Domestication, Opium, Romantic Poetry, Women Poets

In Romantic literature, nature is often depicted as a romanticized and feminised entity which poets find praise worthy for its sublimity. It is often associated with women for similarities in terms of beauty and nurturing element. Romantic literature portrays various representations of nature, its beauty, enormity and an all encompassing sublimity which often works as a tool of escapism through imagination. One such representation is of opium narratives in Romantic poetry. The study aims to take into consideration the use of opium narrative in the women's Romantic poetry, countering the canonical representation by male poets. The beauty and love for nature has been best captured through the movement and genre of Romantic literature. The usual idea of Romantic literature comes as poets yearning for a sense of escape into nature from the harsh struggles of their daily lives, significantly caused by the industrial revolution. In such conditions, opium has been a significant part of Romantic imagination and poetry. While traditionally opium narrative in Romantic poetry has been seen through the male poets' eyes, the current studies counters this narration by looking specifically into the women Romantic poets' use of opium narratives.

The domestication of opium is a cultural phenomenon that is majorly found in the women Romantics poetry. This essay talks about the domestication of opium as a counter discourse by women poets of Romanticism against the male Romantics' idea of escapist sublimity of the 'orient' through opium, and along with it the cultural, social and imperial reasons of this new discourse of opium and how it brought a new light to the relation between opium and Romanticism. It looks at the counter discourse on the use of opium as a herb by women Romantic poets who instead of using it as an exotic phenomena of escapism, domesticise its use as more of a medicine.

When it comes to the depiction of opium in poetry, this realm is canonically dominated by the male Romantic poets. Two of the most famous opium narratives can be found in Samuel Taylor Coleridge's *Kubla Khan* (1816) and Thomas De Quincey's

Confessions of an English Opium-Eater (1821). These narratives depict opium as a means and tool that has transcendental qualities which results in heightening the imagination power of the poet and provides him with the experience of sublimity and works as a means to escape as well, rooted in masculine and colonial imagination. Hannah Cowles Freeman argues that this opium narrative of the male Romantic poets is challenged by the Romantic women poets, she explains that these women poets' poetry "offers a counter discourse to the traditional opium canon" by "incorporating opium use into the domestic hearth, its medicinal effects aiding in their wifely and motherly duties" (Freeman 01). The use of opium became a common thing during the 18th century. It was used by common people on a regular basis for different purposes which mainly included its use for its medicinal benefits. It was used for curing the common and recurring illnesses, on babies to help them sleep quietly and for soothing the body aches. This fact demonstrates that opium was a very much part of the daily domestic life of 18th century England. Historical evidence shows that only in 1868 with the Pharmacy Act, its sale was limited. But despite this depiction of opium has been that of some other place which transcends its consumer to another place as a means of escape in an imaginative frenzy until it was challenged by the Romantic women writers such as Maria Logan, Henrietta O'Neil, Anna Seward and Sara Coleridge. These women poets depict opium as a familiar, domesticated and everyday presence in their lives.

The contrast in the depiction of opium use in male Romantics and women Romantic poets results into the "opium use highlighting a competing discourse of cultural perspectives on opium: one being that it is associated with the 'orient' and one which locates it squarely in the middle class British home" (Freeman 02). This depiction is problematized when one explores the idea of indigenization of opium. Traditionally opium requires warm weather to grow which is not common in England. Opium works as a link between the east and the west. Opium, which was born out of imperialism, has now become a necessity for women

who have no place to articulate their desires and raw emotions and no place to escape from their daily domestic duties. Opium works as a means which allows women to express their desires, the desires which are silenced in male Romantics' poetry. At this juncture, Vandana Shiva's ideas of nature and women exploited parallelly by capitalism and patriarchal science comes into play as it highlights the universality of nature and women's exploitation at the hands of patriarchy, capitalism and industrialized use of natural resources. Shiva's theory of modern reductionist science as a patriarchal project. Shiva articulates the parallel between exploitative modern science and women' marginalisation through it as "Modern reductionist science, like development, turns out to be a patriarchal project, which has excluded women as experts, and has simultaneously excluded ecological and holistic ways of knowing which understand and respect nature's processes and interconnectedness *as science*" (Shiva 14-15).

The spirit of Shiva's ideas is captured vividly in the representative women Romantics' poetry with reference to opium narratives. One of them is Anna Seward (1742-1809). Known as the 'Swan of Lichfield' Seward was also a respected woman of letters besides being an honoured poet of her times. She is majorly known for reviving the sonnet tradition in English poetry. Interested in literature from the early years of her childhood she developed her love for literature by reading Shakespeare and Milton. She was also a regular contributor to major magazines of her times, specifically *Gentleman's Magazine*. In her sonnet *To The Poppy* (1799), she depicts a "love- crazed maid" who smiles "aghast" (660) standing in the field of poppy. This image of a woman expressing her melancholy who has lost her love finding solace in the opium field is quite radical to the image of the female protagonist in the male Romantics' poetry who meets her fate in the face of death when separated from her lover. Anna Seward counters the masculine opium narrative by using the plant as a means to bear pain while at the same time expressing emotions of the speaker. The striking difference through her sonnet lies in her awareness of opium as she calls it, "Thou flimsy, shewy,

melancholy weed” which helps in “lulling grief and pain” (660), instead of eradicating the pain and suffering completely and escaping into an alternative reality of frenzy. This feminised portrayal of opium is much more realistic, familiar and natural in contrast to unrealistic, dreamlike and exotic masculinised portrayal in male Romantics’ poetry. Seward mentions that this herb is able to provide temporary relief to “a love-craz’d Maid” who is, “smiling aghast” (660). This emphasises on the medicinal use of opium for mental sufferings as well and this portrayal is radical as women Romantics portray the rawness of emotions through this where the feminine subject seeks comfort and refuge in the use of opium, instead of meekly succumbing to her pain as objectified by masculine imagination of femininity.

The idea of sublimity is centered on the understanding of one of the major differences in the male Romantics and women Romantic poets' depiction. The idea of sublimity for the male Romantics has been that of a transcendental process which escapes them in order to heighten their imagination. Anne K. Mellor argued about the "domestication of sublimity" (97) which is central to understanding the role of opium in challenging the idea of sublimity. The idea of escape and sublimity in these women poets' writings is different from the male Romantics. The opium which brings sublimity to the male poets is not depicted as a means of sublimity for these women writers but it rather works as a brief moment of being allowed to feel what they are feeling. The ladyhood of women does not allow them to be expressive of their emotions and desires but with the help of opium they can escape these restrictions even if it is just for a while.

Maria Logan, another major poet, wrote her collection of poetry called *Poems on Several Occasions*. It was published in 1793 with an inscription that mentioned that the poet has dedicated this collection to her intimate friends to express gratitude for their consistent company in her years of sickness. Logan has long suffered through sickness and it was during this time she began to use opium to soothe her chronic pain. Due to her illness her writing

practice was affected and imagery of sickness and death looms over in her poetry. In her poem *To Opium* (1793) she talks about the quality to transcend through the healing power of opium. Logan refers to the opium plant as “the balm, whose sov'reign pow'r/ Can still the throb of Pain” (539), emphasising on the medicinal properties of the plant which helps in relieving physical and psychological pain. She states the use of opium as a herbal plant in contrast to capitalist and material wealth. It is significant to note that Logan also mentions the ability of the plant to increase the artistic ability to produce a work of art as she mentions “Reviv'd by thee, my drooping Muse/ Now pours the grateful strain” (440). But the striking difference between the male Romantics use of opium for creating art and Logan’s description that, for Logan opium works as a medicine which helps in soothing her physical and mental discomfort, bringing back her innate ability to produce arts, against the male Romantics use of opium as a magical substance which escapes them into an unnatural and unrealistic artistic frenzy. Similarly Henrietta O’Neill (1758-1793), is another major Romantic poet who wrote on the use of opium in women’s daily lives. O’Neill was the patron and close friend of another Romantic poet Charlotte Smith, on whose request she wrote *Ode to the Poppy*. Her work is significant to understand the realistic use of opium in contrast to its fantasized use by male Romantic poets. In her *Ode to the Poppy* (1792) describes opium as a “Soul-soothing plant” (521). Her focus is on the healing properties of the plant for physical and mental pains. It is useful because of it “the mourner bears to live” (521). Women used opium as a herbal medicine for their everyday aches and pain relief. Such usage stands for the familiarity and accessibility of it in the domestic and feminine space. O’Neill describes this idea as she mentions her use of opium “spread, Thy spell around my aching head...Thy balsam for a broken heart; And by thy soft Lethan power” (521). This is important to note the portal of women romantics is rooted in familiarity, domesticity and medicinal use of opium instead of colonized exotic representation by male poets rooted in patriarchy and exploitation of nature.

As it has been argued in the paper, that women Romantic poets revolutionised the use of opium narratives by domesticating it by reclaiming the male dominated discourse around it which sees it as an exotic drug Sara Coleridge's (1802-1852) narration of opium becomes most vividly feminine and healing. Sara Coleridge was the daughter of renowned Romantic poet Samuel Taylor Coleridge, and Sara Fricker. She was also a translator, editor and wrote extensively on fairy tales and children's literature. These major genres she worked on, also reflect in her poetry taken for the study as she introduces her own son, Herbert in the poem to denote her long years of familiarity with opium. She first began the use of opium in the form of a sedative for better sleep and praised it for its usefulness to provide her relief after long days of physical and mental exhaustion due to her motherly responsibilities. Coleridge's poetry represents that "The women poets discussed here represent a larger cultural phenomenon where mothers and wives used opium on a regular basis for its medicinal purposes, demystifying its administration and its effects on the body" (Freeman 1). In her poem *Poppies* (1834), She brings in her son Herbert and begins by looking at the plant through her young son's curious and joyful eyes, who finds the plant to be as "nothing more /Than other brilliant weeds" (199). This introduction of her son to plant draws a familiar image that associates a sense of familiarity and easiness with the child as well. It highlights the commonality of opium plants in the domestic space, specifically the kitchen that stands for the space central to women and nurturing, which harboured it as an everyday used herb and medicine. Coleridge has been pregnant for a decade when she began to depend heavily on opium to fight against depression. She mentions "When poor Mama long restless lies/ She drinks the poppy's juice" (199). This is why she goes on talking about the significance and healing properties of it to soothe pain caused by daily motherly duties and household chores, in opposition to its exploitative use by the commercialization of it by patriarchal science and capitalism.

The domestication of opium also brings in the question of imperialism and its problematics. The idea of daily use of opium

indicates the fact that opium was grown in the kitchen gardens of many households as England's climate is not suitable for its growth. As much as the idea of growing opium in a kitchen garden, a place for nurturing, is radical in itself, it also questions its problematic aspects. Because this is how imperialism works. It removes an indigenous thing from its native place and plants it elsewhere, and uses it in a totally different manner there. Despite this whole discourse of domesticating opium, it is interesting to notice that its mention in women's writings was still seen as demeaning. The fact all these women poets only use the term 'poppy' indicates the need to censor the word opium for women, especially the ones belonging to the aristocracy. The challenge to the traditional opium narrative of male poets brought by the women writers through its domestication is important to understand the shifting relation between Romanticism and opium and how this provides with a new lense to see it in a gendered narrative of opium being domesticated, a very much part of women's life and it challenges the male idea of sublimity and escapism.

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